

Management of Digital Research Data at the End of a Project

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1. Purpose and Usage of this Document

- This document is aimed primarily at members of the University of Basel.

The document provides **guidelines** with detailed information on key aspects to consider regarding Research Data Management (RDM) at the conclusion of a research project. Additionally, it includes a **checklist** to help keep track of the various steps and tasks. It also includes the special case of **off-boarding** (i.e., leaving a research project or the university). At the end of the document, you find a **glossary**.

This document is designed for handling all types of digital research data, both qualitative and quantitative, including code.

As you approach the completion of a research project, it is essential to address key questions regarding your datasets. Ideally, data publication and preservation should be planned at the beginning of your project using a [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#). We recommend beginning preparations at least 3 to 6 months before project completion to ensure your data are properly documented, transferred and/or stored. As long as there are no legal and ethical constraints, data should be made publicly available for reuse. For complex projects and/or those involving multiple stakeholders, allow more than 6 months before project end for these preparations. Be mindful that costs may arise, e.g. for [data curation](#) and storage solutions after the project ends, which must already be accounted for in the budget at the beginning of the project.

This document applies to different types of research projects. Please be aware that "end of the project" is a broad concept and you should determine what that means in the context of your specific project. Projects can range from individual PhD research to large-scale, multi-year collaborative projects (e.g. NCCR or edition projects). For long-term projects (more than 4 years), it is particularly important to address data management issues regularly and to think in terms of sub-projects or milestones.

If you have questions regarding data management in general or regarding this checklist, please contact the [data steward of your institution](#) or get in touch with the RDM Network coordination via researchdata@unibas.ch.

2. Guidelines

2.1. Comply with the Relevant Regulations and Requirements

“Research data generated as part of University of Basel research projects generally remain the property of the University of Basel.” (Art. 4 (9), Integrity Regulations) “This [...] applies to all members of the University of Basel who engage in academic work as part of research groups at the University of Basel or at associated institutions on behalf of the University of Basel.” (Art. 1 (1), Integrity Regulations) As a member of the university, you must therefore follow its regulations. In particular, you must follow the University’s [Integrity Regulations](#) (legally non-binding [English translation](#) available) and the [Policy on Research Data Management](#) regarding the handling of research data.

If your project is funded by a research funding organization, ensure that you understand and meet their specific requirements for data publication and preservation.

For research involving personal data, you must comply with applicable legal regulations and [ethical guidelines](#). This includes adhering to research ethics principles – such as honoring the informed consent ([UEK template](#) and [further information by DPO](#)) signed by research participants – as well as any contracts or agreements established within the project, e.g. with regard to deletion of data. Follow the [data protection law of the Canton of Basel-Stadt](#). Additionally, if your research involves health-related personal data (e.g., human diseases, the structure and function of the human body), the [Federal Act on Research Involving Human Beings](#) and its ordinances must be followed. For clinical trials, the data retention requirement is as follows: “The investigator must retain all documents required for the identification and follow-up of participants, and all other original data, for at least twenty years after the completion or premature termination of the clinical trial.” (Art. 45, ClinO). For more information, see the university’s [checklist on working with personal data](#).

2.2. Know your Responsibilities

As a project lead:

According to the Integrity Regulations of the University of Basel, the project lead – typically the principal investigator (PI) – is generally responsible for the research data. At the end of the project, this means they need to ensure “adequate storage of the research findings, their accessibility and compliance with the University of Basel’s data protection and archiving requirements.” (Art. 4 (8), Integrity Regulations)

The project lead may delegate data management responsibilities to another person. However, this should be a person with appropriate data management skills, as well as a long-term contract (ideally, a permanent position) to ensure continuity. Responsibilities and tasks for each project member should be clearly clarified and documented at the beginning of the project in the data management plan (DMP), and updated as needed over time.

For project leads of clinical trials, specific regulations apply as outlined in the [Ordinance on Clinical Trials](#) (Art. 3,4,5,6, ClinO). For project leads of studies classified as "Human Research with the Exception of Clinical Trials", specific regulatory conditions according to the [Human Research Ordinance](#) (HRO Art. 3 and 4) apply.

As a PhD student or researcher (postdoc, research staff):

If your research is part of a larger project or research group, the PI holds primary responsibility for data management. You should consult them regarding the project's guidelines and processes for data management, and ensure you follow them since you will most likely be the person who executes management of your research data. Therefore, read the detailed information on the checklist contents carefully. Additionally, there should be a written statement outlining procedures to follow when completing your PhD or respective (sub)project, covering aspects such as data handover to the university, access and storage. Follow specifications regarding RDM in your contract. As a PhD student, you must also adhere to the [doctoral degree regulations of your faculty](#). If no RDM guidelines are specified in your contract or the doctoral degree regulations, the University's Integrity Regulations apply.

If you are an individual PhD student not affiliated with a research group (i.e., without a working contract at the university), you are responsible for managing your own data. You must follow the doctoral degree regulations of your faculty and should adhere to the University's Integrity Regulations and RDM policy.

As a researcher at the University Hospital Basel:

If you are conducting research at the University Hospital Basel (USB), you must comply with the hospital's specific regulations on data management. For details, refer to the "[Weisung Aufbewahrung, Archivierung und Löschung medizinischer Dokumentation](#)" (accessible only to USB members).

2.3. Review, Organize and Document your Data

Considerations: To ensure smooth research data management, incorporate interim steps such as regular backups, secure storage, and metadata updates. Additionally, consider implementing periodic data cleaning days to maintain data integrity and organization.

Steps to be taken:

1. **Update the Data Management Plan (DMP)**

Ensure the DMP accurately reflects the current status of your data and any future needs, including permissions and access controls for collaborators or supervisors, or long-term storage solutions to preserve data beyond the project's completion.

2. **Clean up data on the storage infrastructure**

- Copy all personal documents (e.g. job applications, diplomas, working contracts) to a private storage.
- Make sure all project-related data are in a research project folder and not in your private storage.

3. **Identify data to keep (= assess data value):**

Assess the value of your datasets to determine which should be retained.

Core datasets that should be kept are data that:

- support research outcomes and conclusions,
- are of scientific or historical value (e.g., time documentation, unique data),
- cost more to reproduce than to store, or where reproduction is impossible,
- ensure research integrity and reproducibility,
- offer future benefits, such as contribution to greater data collections, intergenerational comparison,

- have potential for reuse, for example in research, teaching, training, or collaborations (reuse depends on metadata quality, completeness, integrity, accessibility and readability of the data, licenses, and rights allowing reuse),
- comply with ethical, legal, and regulatory requirements.

Consider your data processing workflow:

- Retain all information necessary for reproducing research results.
- Determine whether raw data must be kept. In some cases, keeping them is essential, in others not (e.g. interview recordings vs. transcripts).

4. **Identify data to delete:** Deletion of unnecessary data helps reduce lab or departmental storage usage.

Consider deleting:

- data containing personal identifiers that cannot be anonymized, unless agreed on in the informed consent,
- duplicate (exact copies), irrelevant or redundant datasets, unless they are essential for reproducibility (e.g., technical or biological replicates),
- drafts or other intermediary versions that do not contribute to research findings.

5. **Delete all data no longer needed:** If unsure about deletion, consult your PI. Additional guidance is available on the RDM website ([‘Selecting research data’](#)).

6. **Create final documentation for all remaining datasets**

Thorough documentation enhances data discoverability and reusability.

- Document the data’s context, methodology, collection process details, and any transformations, e.g. in [README files or codebooks](#).
- Use standardized metadata formats (e.g., [Dublin Core](#), [DataCite](#)) for ease of discovery and reuse.
- Record [versioning](#) details (e.g. via Git), especially if the data have been revised during the project.

7. **Check file organization**

Ensure remaining files are well-structured and easily discoverable:

- Use [clear, consistent naming conventions](#) (e.g., dataset_date_version).
- Convert data to [open, long-term usable formats](#) to ensure long-term accessibility.

2.4. Identify Mid- and Long-term Storage Solutions for your Data

Considerations: All core research data should be preserved after the end of a project for a specific retention period to ensure research integrity. Typically, this period ranges from 1 to 20 years (**mid-term storage**). Certain datasets – such as climate data and cultural heritage data, which cannot be regenerated – should be archived indefinitely (**long-term storage**).

In general, it is recommended to publish research datasets as comprehensively as possible.

If some data have not yet been published or cannot be published due to legal or ethical constraints, ensure they are securely stored. If publication imposes restrictions on data reuse, consider keeping a backup copy in secure storage.

Storage scenarios may include:

- All core research data are openly available in a [repository](#).
- Some data are stored in a repository, while others that cannot be shared openly remain on university servers.
- All data are stored exclusively on university servers.

Steps to be taken:

1. **Review storage options**

An overview of storage solutions according to the type of research data can be found here: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/storage/>. Contact [sciCORE](#) or [ITS](#) about possible (mid-/long-term) storage solutions.

2. **Determine the retention period:** Sometimes different retention periods apply to different parts of a research dataset, see the RDM website ([‘Requirements’](#)) for details. The **University of Basel expects a minimum of 5 years** for data retention ([Art. 4 \(8\), Integrity Regulations](#)). However, many research sponsors are demanding longer data retention; for example, **the SNSF recommends 10 years** ([SNF, FAQ Preservation and long-term storage of research data](#)).

3. Before transferring data to mid-term storage, **establish a formal agreement** regarding the process and responsibilities for deleting the data once the retention period has expired. This agreement must be coordinated with and approved by the storage provider(s).

4. **Define access regulation** for former project members. To this end, set up an agreement with the PI and/or institute head and coordinate with IT how to ensure continued access when necessary. Check the RDM website ([‘Data Access Regulations’](#)) for key considerations to include in the agreement.

5. **Delete data after a specific retention period**

- For data managed by the research group (e.g., in an “archive” folder), the PI decides whether data can be deleted.
- If the PI is no longer available (e.g. has left the university without a forwarding address), the manager (Geschäftsführer) of the former PI’s department makes the decision.
- Provide documentation (e.g. a README file) specifying who is responsible for the data, when to delete the data (specify date), and what to do if none of the responsible individuals are available anymore.
- For data on [sciCORE Deep Storage](#), the dataset registry determines when data can be deleted (this is registered at the time of submission as “retention period”). sciCORE does not delete data without a mandate from the researcher. In sciCORE Deep Storage, the preservation period is predetermined (by the PI). In principle, data can be deleted automatically after this period, but sciCORE will confirm before deletion.

2.5. Publish your Data

Considerations: Certain repositories require advance notice – at least 3 to 6 months before the end of the project – to properly curate the data. Ideally, you should contact the repository of your choice already at the start of the project to clarify the structure and documentation needed for data publication.

Steps to be taken:

1. Identify data for publication

Check whether there are any datasets from your project that you have not yet published but would like/should make publicly available to others. Publish data that are reusable, significant, and have potential value to the society and/or the academic community.

2. Check the **specific requirements of your university, journal and/or funding organization** with regard to data publication.

Consider potential costs, especially for large datasets. Be aware of restrictions, such as confidential or sensitive information, contractual limitations, [copyright](#) and [licenses](#), and authorization timeframes.

3. **Select an appropriate repository to publish your data** according to the [FAIR](#) and [CARE](#) principles.

The University of Basel does not have an institutional repository, we recommend using a [discipline-specific repository](#). Ensure data are stored in compliance with university policies, requirements of the funding organization and legal obligations.

2.6. Organize the Transfer for your Data

Considerations: Research data may need to be transferred from its current storage location to another (e.g. another university, archive storage, a repository, etc.). Plan the data transfer well in advance – ideally at the start of the project, but no later than 3 to 6 months before project end.

Steps to be taken:

1. Plan the data transfer

- Assess data sensitivity, as this determines the transfer method.
- Check legal obligations, including whether informed consent or ethics agreements allow long-term preservation and reuse for research purposes. When working with personal data, refer to our checklist [Dealing with Personal Data in Research](#) for useful tips.
- For security-related concerns, get in touch with the [Data Protection Officer's](#) team.
- Get in touch with your local Research IT team, [IT Services](#) or (for large, sensitive, or sensitive personal data sets) with [sciCORE](#) to decide on a suitable transfer method.
- Organize data transfer and use/processing agreements (DTUA/DTPA) if needed (e.g. transfer outside of the university). See examples here: <https://sphn.ch/services/dtua/>.
- Ensure that the data stay with the home university if the PI moves to another university. If the data must leave the university, establish a formal agreement guaranteeing that the university retains access to the data. Lastly, assess if any researcher or collaborator needs to keep a copy.

2. Transfer the data

- Choose the correct transfer tool and method based on data sensitivity.
- Encrypt sensitive data during transfer and use a tool that logs the transfer for auditing purposes.
- Refer to transfer method recommendations on the RDM website (see [‘Data Transfer Solutions’](#)).
- Ensure data integrity:
 - Involve storage providers for any larger data transfer.
 - Use [checksums](#) to ensure data integrity.
 - First copy the data to the new location, and then check integrity and completeness before deleting the original files.

2.7. Arrange a Final Data Management Appointment and Prepare Access Agreements

After completing the steps above, schedule an [appointment](#) with your project leader, supervisor, or head of department, where you show the location of your data and that you processed them according to the checklist. Ideally, both parties [sign a confirmation](#) that all information regarding the data have been handed over appropriately. We recommend signing the [final checklist](#) and storing the signed file, e.g. together with the final project folder. If needed, set up an additional document regarding future data access (see recommendations on [Data Access Regulations](#)).

3. Checklist

A. General Considerations

- Check and comply with the **relevant regulations and requirements**.
- Know and review your **responsibilities** as PI, PhD student, postdoc or research staff.

B. Review, Organize and Document your Data

- Update the Data Management Plan (DMP)** to reflect the current status of your data and future needs (permissions, access controls, storage solutions).
- Create final documentation for all datasets using standardized metadata formats** e.g. in [README files or codebooks](#).
- Clean up data on the storage infrastructure** and make sure all project-related data are in a research project folder and not on your private storage.
 - Identify data to keep** that are core datasets, which support research outcomes and conclusions, enables research integrity, reproducibility, or has potential for reuse, for example in future research, in teaching, training, or future collaborations.
 - Identify data to delete:** Deletion of dispensable data helps reduce lab or departmental storage usage.
 - Delete all data no longer needed:** In case of uncertainty, discuss with your PI.
- Check file organization** to ensure the data are discoverable, readable and manageable.

C. Identify Mid- and Long-term Storage Solutions for your Data

- Review storage options** according to the type of research data: <https://researchdata.unibas.ch/en/storage/> and contact [sciCORE](#) or [ITS](#) about possible (mid-/long-term) storage solutions.
- Determine retention period:** Different retention periods may apply to different parts of a dataset from a research project.
- Establish a formal agreement** regarding the process and responsibilities for deleting the data once the retention period has expired before transferring data to mid-term storage.
- Define access regulation** for former project members, set up an agreement with their PI and/or head of the institute and check with IT how to guarantee access.
- Delete data after a specific retention period:** Clarify with project lead, and provide documentation who is responsible for the data and when the data can be deleted if none of the responsible individuals is available anymore.

D. Publish your Data

- Identify data for publication:** Check if there are any data sets from your project that you have not yet published but should be made publicly available to others.
- Check the specific requirements of your university, journal and/or funding organization with regard to data publication**, and be aware of potential costs, restrictions, copyright and licenses.
- Select an appropriate repository to publish your data** according to the [FAIR](#) and [CARE](#) principles, using a [discipline-specific repository](#).

E. Organize the Transfer of your Data

- Plan the data transfer** by assessing data sensitivity, and get in touch with your local Research IT team, [IT Services](#) or (for large, sensitive, or sensitive personal data sets) with [sciCORE](#) to decide on a suitable transfer method.
- Transfer the data** by evaluating different transfer methods ([‘Data Transfer Solutions’](#)) and by ensuring data integrity.

F. Arrange a Final Data Management Appointment and Prepare Access Agreements

- Arrange a final data management appointment** with your project leader/supervisor/head of department.
- Sign a **confirmation document** (e.g. this checklist) stating appropriate handover and potential agreements regarding future data use/access.
- Store the final checked and signed file**, e.g. together with final project folder.

Describe which steps in the checklist could **NOT** be performed and why:

List **location of documents** (confirmation document, agreements regarding future data use/access):

Date, Place
(researcher)

Date/Place
(PI/Department Head/responsible person)

4. Special Case: Off-Boarding

If you are about to leave a research project or the university, first of all you should always inform your supervisor (e.g. your PI or, if you are a PI, your department or faculty head) and review, organize and document your data as explained in section 3.1.

With a clear overview of your data, understand whether or not you will still need access to the data or part of it after you have left.

If you no longer need access to the data, talk to your supervisor for the details of the data handover and follow the steps in the checklist as applicable.

Your aim should be to ensure that no relevant data are lost, inaccessible or incomprehensible for other members of the research project or the department after you have left, and that it is clearly defined who is responsible for the remaining data from now on.

- Please note that access rights are not automatically transferred after you leave a research project or the university. Make sure that ownership of all project folders, project software and data infrastructures for which you are the main owner is transferred to the relevant person (e.g. ELN, storage on sciCORE+, etc.). Contact your supervisor and IT Services for this.
- Be aware that after leaving the university your personal university account including your personal storage and personal email account will be deleted after 6 months. Do not forget them when you review, organize and document your data.

If you still need access to the data, do the same as above, additionally make sure it is clearly regulated how you will have access to the data after you have left (see recommendations on [Data Access Regulations](#)). Clarify with your supervisor what data must stay at the university, what data you are allowed to copy and what data you may transfer to a new location.

- Examples of this case include PhD students prolonging their PhD projects without a working contract at the university, or principle investigators moving to another University with their research projects.

If possible, provide personal contact information before you leave in case of further questions.

5. Glossary

Accessibility: Ensuring that research data can be retrieved, used, and understood by authorized users under well-defined conditions. This includes proper documentation, metadata, adherence to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), and compliance with legal or ethical restrictions.

Anonymized data: Data that have been stripped of all personally identifiable information, making re-identification impossible.

Archive: A repository used for the long-term, secure storage of data, particularly for historical or completed research, ensuring its availability for future reference or replication while maintaining its integrity. Archives are often a key part of long-term preservation strategies. An archive is curated and may not be publicly available.

Data processing: Any handling of data, irrespective of the means and procedures used, in particular the collection, storage, keeping, use, modification, disclosure, archiving, deletion or destruction of data. In the context of personal data, it is defined in Art. 3 (5), IDG BS:
https://www.gesetzsammlung.bs.ch/app/de/texts_of_law/153.260.

Data readability: Refers to the ability to process the information on a computer system or device other than the one that initially created the digital information or on which it is currently stored. Typically, non-readability involves some aspect of an older storage device (a tape or disk) that makes it physically incompatible with existing equipment. This hardware obsolescence occurs when storage devices and media used today become incompatible with those developed in the future.

Data transfer: The movement of research data between systems, institutions, or collaborators, ensuring integrity, security, and compliance with regulations. Methods include encrypted file transfers, secure repositories, and controlled access platforms.

Dataset: A structured collection of related data (points), often organized in tables, spreadsheets, or databases. It can include raw or processed data and may contain qualitative, quantitative, or mixed data types, used for analysis and research.

Deletion (of data): The process of permanently removing research data from storage systems to prevent recovery. This can include soft deletion (data marked for removal but still recoverable) or hard deletion (irreversible erasure), following institutional policies, legal requirements, and ethical considerations. Secure deletion methods may be required for sensitive or personal data.

End of project: The formal conclusion of a research project, marked by final data analysis, reporting, publication, and, where applicable, archiving or sharing of research data according to data management and preservation guidelines. End of project is a broad term. Examples include when the funding from the research sponsor expires and a project is formally completed; or the project ends once all publications and doctoral theses have been released.

Health-related personal data: Information concerning the health or disease of a specific or identifiable person, including genetic data.

Integrity: The accuracy, consistency, and trustworthiness of research data throughout its life cycle. Ensuring data integrity involves preventing unauthorized changes, errors, or corruption, and maintaining data quality through secure storage, regular checks, and validation methods.

Logging: Refers to the systematic recording of events and activities during the data transfer process. This includes capturing details such as timestamps, source and destination addresses, file names, transfer status, and any errors encountered. Effective logging ensures transparency, aids in troubleshooting, and supports auditing by providing a detailed trail of actions taken during data transfers.

Long-term storage / preservation: The process of maintaining data for extended periods (often decades or more), ensuring its integrity, accessibility, and usability. Preservation strategies aim for indefinite storage, typically over 100+ years, using stable formats and secure infrastructures to safeguard the data for future generations.

Metadata: Data that provide descriptive, structural, or administrative information about other data, helping with organization, discovery, and interpretation. Examples include author, creation date, file format, keywords, and data origin.

Mid-term storage / deep storage: Data stored for a period ranging from a few months to several years, typically for ongoing or completed projects. Data are kept for research integrity or reuse. They are optimized for retrieval when needed, but not intended for indefinite retention.

Permission & access control: Mechanisms that regulate who can view, modify, or share research data. This includes role-based access, authentication, and authorization to ensure data security and compliance with legal or ethical requirements.

Personal data: Any information referring to a definite or definable natural person. (Art. 3 (3), IDG BS: https://www.gesetzessammlung.bs.ch/app/de/texts_of_law/153.260). (See also “Sensitive Personal Data”).

Processed data: Data that has been cleaned, transformed, or analyzed to derive meaning or insights.

Project: A structured research endeavor with defined objectives, methodology, and timeline, involving data collection, analysis, and dissemination of findings.

Pseudonymized data: Data where identifying details are replaced with pseudonyms, allowing re-identification with additional information.

Raw data: Unprocessed, original data collected from experiments, surveys, or observations.

Research data: Any data collected, observed, or generated during research, serving as evidence for findings. It is material that can vary greatly depending on the discipline and research area and is created through various methods such as measurements, experiments, surveys, interviews, digitization and much more Types of data (examples):

- **Qualitative data:** Non-numerical data, such as interviews, texts, or images, used to explore concepts and meanings.
- **Quantitative data:** Numerical data, often analyzed statistically, including measurements, survey results, and computational outputs.
- **Code:** Scripts, algorithms, or software used for data processing, analysis, or modeling in research.

Retention period: The length of time research data are kept before they are deleted or archived. The retention period is often determined by legal, ethical, or institutional guidelines and can vary based on the type of data and its intended use.

Sensitive data: Data that require special protection by law or contractual confidentiality obligations or due to its critical nature, e.g. trade secrets, research data under embargo, or classified information.

Sensitive personal data / special personal data (“besondere Personendaten”): In accordance with [Art. 3 \(4\), IDG BS](#):

- a) Personal data whose processing poses a particular danger of violating a fundamental right, in particular information about
 1. religious, ideological, political or trade union opinions;
 2. health, genetic background, personal privacy, sexual life, sexual orientation or ethnic origin;
 3. social security measures;
 4. administrative or criminal prosecutions and sanctions;
 5. physical, physiological or behavioral characteristics of a natural person, obtained by using special technical procedures which enable or confirm the unique identification of that person (biometric data);
- b) compilations of information that enable the evaluation of crucial aspects of the personality of a natural person (personality profile)